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crystalline solids, which were washed with a little acetone and dry ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 . Analytical results show the complexes have 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometric composition.

In the second step, ethanolic suspension of the complex was treated with excess of veratraldoxime solution and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath at $\sim 70^\circ$. On cooling, the separated compounds were washed with acetone, dry ether and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were obtained in powder-form.

Structural Studies of some Mixed Ligand Dimeric Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)

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WE report here the synthesis and characterisation of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} mixed complexes with 3-(dimethylaminomethyl)indole and veratraldoxime.

Experimental

The reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Veratraldoxime was obtained in a manner similar to that employed for salicylaldoxime¹ except that the crystals were obtained after standing the concentrated solution for 36 h at room temperature. 3-(Dimethylaminomethyl)indole was prepared by the literature procedure².

Preparation of complexes: A two-step process was employed. In the first step, ethanolic solution of the Mannich base and the respective metal salt was mixed in the molar ratio 2 : 1.1 : 1 and refluxed at $80-85^\circ$ for ~ 30 min. The light green, dark green, and pinkish complexes were separated as

Results and Discussion

Analytical results (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1 : 1 (M : L : L', where $\text{L} = \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$ and $\text{L}' = \text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$) stoichiometry for the complexes. The compounds are not soluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. They melt at higher temperature ($300-30^\circ$). The molecular weight data (Rast camphor method) of the complexes favour for a dimeric structure for these complexes. The complexes are non-electrolytes as evidenced by molar conductance data in DMF ($4-6 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$).

The magnetic moments (corrected for temperature independent paramagnetism) of the Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes are 1.55, 2.04 and 4.21 B.M. respectively. The observed values are less than the spin-only value for mononuclear octahedral complexes having no major interactions between two metal moieties³. The low magnetic moments of the complexes are attributed to spin-coupling within the dimer.

Six-coordinated Cu^{II} complexes possess two or more bands in the region 5-16 kK. The complex (solution in DMF) shows a broad electronic spectral band at $12\,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to the transition, ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, a characteristic of the distorted octahedral Cu^{II} complex⁴. The broadening may be due to Jahn-Teller effect, since the 2E_g state is susceptible to Jahn-Teller distortion.

Three peaks have been observed in the spectra of the Ni^{II} complex at 9 450, 15 100 and 25 450 cm^{-1} which have been assigned to the transitions⁵, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$. These are in accordance to the octahedral geometry⁵ around Ni^{II} . The value of ν_2/ν_1 is 1.597 which in agreement with the value

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol wt. (Found/Calcd)
	N	Metal	Cl	
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{M}_{11}\text{NO}_3)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}]$	9.23 (9.27)	13.89 (14.03)	7.80 (7.82)	859 (453.02)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}]$	9.38 (9.37)	13.16 (13.09)	7.89 (7.91)	822 (448.14)
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}]$	9.38 (9.36)	13.02 (13.14)	7.81 (7.90)	804 (448.39)

required for octahedral complexes of Ni^{II}. The calculated values for 10 *Dq* and *B* are 9 249 and 944 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Electronic spectra (in DMF) of the Co^{II} complex display three bands around 7 950, 16 250 and 19 200 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the spin-allowed transitions, ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(F) (ν₃) respectively. The appearance of these bands suggests octahedral environment⁶ around Co^{II}. This stereochemistry of the Co^{II} complex is supported by the value of ν₂/ν₁ (2.05) which lies between 1.8 and 2.2, obtained for octahedral complexes. The values for 10 *Dq* and *B* are 9 310 and 970 cm⁻¹ respectively.

The ν_{NH} band (3 390 cm⁻¹) in the ir spectrum of 3-(dimethylaminomethyl)indole is not traceable in the spectra of the complexes, indicating the deprotonation and subsequent formation of metal-nitrogen bonding. A medium band observed at 1 150 cm⁻¹ (C-N) of aliphatic t-amine in the above ligand appeared at ~1 110 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, which is suggestive of the coordination of nitrogen atom of C-N with the metal.

The ir spectrum of veratraldehyde oxime showed a strong band at ~3 300 cm⁻¹ and a medium one at 3 200 cm⁻¹, characteristic of symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching vibrations of OH in N-OH group⁷. These bands remain unaltered in the spectra of the complexes, showing the non-involvement of this group in complexation. A sharp band at 1 660 cm⁻¹ (C=N) of the oxime group⁸ shows a negative shift of 20–25 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, which shows the participation of the azomethine nitrogen in complex formation. The symmetrical stretching band at 1 045 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C) gets shifted to lower frequency region (1 020–1 015 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, which clearly shows that the oxygen atom of the methoxy groups also takes part in chelation. Thus azomethine nitrogen and oxygen atom of the methoxy groups are the coordination sites in this ligand.

The non-ligand bands at ~500–520 and 400–410 cm⁻¹ may be due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively. The low frequency band at 230–225 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, is tentatively assigned to stretching vibration of metal linked to bridged halogen. Because the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature, sixth coordination position of metal is occupied by chlorine atom.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of New Mixed Azomethyne Schiff Base Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) and their Pyridine Adducts involving β-Diketones as Ligands

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METAL complexes of symmetrical azomethynes (imine complexes) have been widely studied¹.

During recent years a few complexes of mixed azomethynes have also been reported². In the present investigation new types of mixed ligand imine Schiff base complexes of the type MLL'.2H₂O, where, M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}; L=acetylacetonimine, L'=benzoylacetonimine or 1,3-diphenyl-3-iminepropen-1-ol or L=benzoylacetonimine and L'=1,3-diphenyl-3-iminepropen-1-ol have been synthesised. The pyridine adducts of the mixed imine Schiff base complexes have also been prepared. The relative stability of the complexes have been described by thermogravimetric studies.

Experimental

Acetylacetone, benzoylacetonimine, dibenzoylmethane (Fluka), pyridine, cupric nitrate, nickel nitrate and cobalt nitrate hydrated were of A.R. grade. Ethanol, chloroform and benzene were purified by distillation before use.

Preparation of imine Schiff base complexes: To the cobalt, nickel or copper nitrate aqueous solution (0.2 mol) an excess of liquor ammonia was added till the hydroxide formed and dissolved resulting in the formation of metalamine complex. To it was added an alcoholic solution (0.2 mol) of acetylacetone and benzoylacetonimine or dibenzoylmethane, or benzoylacetonimine and dibenzoylmethane so that the metal and the two ligands were in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h in case of nickel compounds and 2 h for cobalt and copper compounds with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was then poured on an evaporating dish where the solid complexes were obtained immediately in case of cobalt and copper compounds, while in case of nickel the solid was obtained after 0.5 h. The resulting crystalline solid was washed with water and ethanol and air-dried.